

Functional Areas of Business Sustainable Finance – Environmental Social and Governance - From Billions to Trillions

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Executive Summary

Introduction

The United Nations Member States agreed and adopted in 2015, the implementation of the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The purpose of these goals is to build a more prosperous, more equal, and more secure world by the year 2030. The 17 Goals are interlinked, and to leave no one behind, it is important that we achieve them all by 2030. It is a call for action by all countries-rich, poor, middle income – to end poverty, promote prosperity while protecting the planet.

Global Context

Investors across the globe are becoming more aware and conscious about investing in areas that create a positive development impact. Over the last decade, this type of impact focused investing has gained importance as an investment model that aims to achieve not just financial return but also positive social or environmental development impact.

ESG Factors

SDG targets helps investors to identify if their investments are “sustainable” to all stakeholders and thereby helps in achieving these targets. One key aspect is that investors are becoming socially responsible. Another key factor is also that when the social, environment, governance factors are considered in decision-making, it helps identify the risks and opportunities better for the specific investment than the conventional finance-only focused decisions.

Funding Gap for SDGs

SDGs will require investments between US\$5 to \$7 trillion per year, with an investment gap in emerging markets of about \$2.5 trillion per year. This means in addition to funding from respective governments, multilateral financial institutions and other development aids (ODA), we need to build an ecosystem where private capital will play a key role and each dollar of funding has a multiplier effect on social goals to meet the objective of universality (“Leave No One Behind”).

India and SDGs

The estimated funding gap to achieve SDGs by 2030 by India is at \$8-10 trillion in total and per year the average gap is approx. \$600billion. Its critical to put SDGs at the core of not just planning but also implementation of investment projects and its monitoring.

Financial Sector in India

Investors of today are continuously re-assessing the traditional investment model and are looking at ways to mitigate risk across climate, data security and regulatory breaches. As providers of capital, this becomes the most important sector which if regulated and managed well, can lead to toxic and dirty capital make way for cleaner and greener funds for developing a sustainable world.

Introduction

The United Nations Member States agreed and adopted in 2015, the implementation of the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The purpose of these goals is to build a more prosperous, more equal, and more secure world by the year 2030. The 17 Goals are interlinked, and to leave no one behind, it is important that we achieve them all by 2030. It is a call for action by all countries-rich, poor, middle income – to end poverty, promote prosperity while protecting the planet. As the clock ticks towards 2030, there is an urgent need for all countries to make more focused investments and policy implementations.

Given the need of the hour to focus on having a better world for all, it is important to think beyond financial returns and to include social, development impact aspects. The objectives of this paper are therefore as follows:

- (a) to define and explain the importance of “sustainable finance” in today’s global context and its linkages with SDGs
- (b) to showcase why “sustainable finance” is critical for our country’s development
- (c) to outline for a key sector in India (ie financial institutions and banks) on the way forward to achieving “sustainable finance” – challenges, opportunities and next steps.

Global Context

Sustainable finance as defined by experts broadly refers to any form of financial service which integrates environment, social, governance (ESG) and other development impact criteria into decision making that provides long term benefits for all the stakeholders involved.

Investors across the globe are becoming more aware and conscious about investing in areas that create a positive development impact. Over the last decade, this type of impact focused investing has gained importance as an investment model that aims to achieve not just financial return but also positive social or environmental development impact. One key aspect is that investors are becoming socially responsible. Another key factor is also that when ESG factors are considered in decision-making, it helps identify the risks and opportunities better for the specific investment than the conventional finance-only focused decisions. Studies by experts have shown that the companies that have strong

ESG ratings are less vulnerable to systematic market risks and thus more attractive to investors. Also, many socially responsible investors avoid investing in companies that have low ESG ratings.

What do investors think globally? GIIN (Global Impact Investing Network)'s ninth Annual Impact Investor Survey in 2019 obtained survey responses from about 260 respondents across DFIs, fund managers, banks, foundations, pension funds across developed markets and emerging markets, revealed the following:

- The impact investing industry is diverse.
- The impact investing market continues to grow and mature.
- Impact measurement and management is central to investors' goals and practices.
- Impact investors report performance in line with both financial and impact expectations.
- Impact investors indicate commitment to developing the industry

Based on similar survey four years ago and the recent survey in 2019 (both by GIIN), they found a 17% CAGR over these four years, with strongest growth in MENA (CAGR of 43%) and South Asia (CAGR of 24%). The respondents also forecast a strong future growth as given below both in terms of count and volume of investments. (extract from GIIN Annual Impact survey 2019)

	Capital invested (USD millions)		Number of investments	
	2018 reported	2019 planned	2018 reported	2019 planned
Mean	128	146	52	59
Median	15	20	7	6
Sum	33,330	37,266	13,303	15,216
Aggregate % growth (projected)	-	13%	-	14%

n = 258

Note: Excludes five outliers and three respondents that did not report 2018 investment activity.

Source: GIIN

How do we determine these ESG factors? We understand based on the above that impact investing is a growing market. The next step is to identify the various ESG factors. This where the SDG targets and climate forum in Paris commitments comes into help in setting up the criteria. It helps investors fulfil their ambition of being a socially responsible investor and provides opportunities for focused investments in these key sectors. Nearly more than 70% of the investors worldwide are willing to pay more for goods and services from companies whose values aligns with theirs (extract from ESG and financial performance: aggregated evidence from more than 2000 empirical studies', Journal of Sustainable Finance and Investment, Gunnar Friede, Timo Busch, Alexander Bassen, 2015).

Funding needs for SDGs

The United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD) estimates the funding needs for achieving the SDGs to be between US\$5 to \$7 trillion per year. The shortfall in emerging markets is estimated to be about \$2.5 trillion per year. This means in addition to funding from respective governments, multilateral financial institutions and other development aids (ODA), we need to build an ecosystem where private capital will play a key role and each dollar of funding has a multiplier effect on social goals to meet the objective of universality ("Leave No One Behind"). Recent study and report on impact investing by International Finance Corporation (IFC) – a member of the World Bank Group, indicates that about \$269 trillion is available as global financial assets held by various stakeholders (like institutions, households etc). It is believed by experts that if we could channel even at least 10-20% of these towards investment on social sectors, it would help us reach our SDG targets.

Similarly, per UN, the financing for achieving all the SDGs within the time limit is possible, given our size and scale of the global financial system (with gross world product and global gross

private sector financial assets estimated at over US\$ 80 trillion (World Bank Databank, 2017) and US\$ 200 trillion respectively (Allianz Global Wealth Report, 2018)). However, the concern is that the funding available (both public and private) are not properly directed towards sustainable development at the pace required in order to reach the targets by 2030.

As mentioned by International Monetary Fund (IMF) in its report on “moving the money to finance the 2030 agenda for development”, we see that we have been achieving progress thus far: for example, in the past few decades the child mortality has fallen significantly; and more than a billion people have moved out of extreme poverty. These achievements portray the power of development efforts, especially when seen at the global context. We still have a long way to go, i.e. all countries need increase their investments across social sectors at a significant rate to achieve the targets universally.

Per UN, it's clear that investing in the SDGs does provide an overall positive impact, as achieving the SDGs is estimated to provide about US\$ 12 trillion of market opportunities and create 380 million new jobs. Further any positive steps on climate change would result in savings of about US\$ 26 trillion by 2030 (Business and Sustainable Development Commission, 2017; Better Business Better World; Report of the Global Commission on the Economy and Climate, 2018).

The need of the hour is to think of ways of mobilizing sustainable funding with focus on ESG, development impact – like blended finance, impact investing like green bonds, ESG fund products and a range of innovative products that assist corporations to shape their strategy and business activities in line with the SDGs.

India and SDGs

We are at the brink of a global transformation. In 2015, India adopted the (SDGs) as a national agenda and along with UNDP, she is working to frame its development plans and socio-economic policies to reach the target by 2030. The 17 SDGs are split across 169 targets which are monitored via 232 indicators. A study of Financial requirements and Gaps of achieving SDGs by India (a report submitted in 2015 by Technology and Action for Rural Advancement, A Social Enterprise of Development Alternatives Group, also supported by UNDP and Ministry of Environment, Government of India) indicates that the estimated funding gap to achieve SDGs by 2030 is at \$8-10 trillion in total and per year the average gap is approx. \$600billion (kindly note that the study was made in 2015 and the actual estimates might be higher)

The current combined annual budget for our country is at \$400billion and the funding gap is almost double the size of our annual budget. Hence, achieving the SDGs will require increasing finance from billions to trillions. To make this possible, we will need to look at way to increase domestic revenue, bring efficiencies in our domestic spend where applicable and exploring options of funding from cross border and private capital.

The good news is that we have already taken the initial steps by setting in place a SDGs Index and dashboard for India - by NITI Ayog highlighting the tracking of the progress made in achieving the SDGs in India against the goals and indicators till date. This is a great effort forward to progress as we do have a mechanism for tracking the progress of the goals to help our central and state governments and other stakeholders determine areas requiring more focus and prioritizing on those sectors.

We are now an economy of \$3 trillion and with a target to achieve \$5 trillion economy by 2025. This would mean a growth rate of over 10-12% per year to reach this, while a realistic and sustainable rate is expected to be at around 6-8%. To achieve this, the focus areas of increasing investment are in manufacturing, infrastructure, financial sector and farming. Its critical to put

SDGs at the core of not just planning but also implementation of investment projects and its monitoring.

Why achieving SDGs is important for our country? Let's first look at some of the challenges or roadblocks that are listed out in the most recent World Bank Group's Systematic Country Diagnostic (SCD) document for India for FY18-22 and some that we gathered during the research. It lists out certain things we face and see in our daily life.

- (a) India is currently constrained on existing natural resources – for example: the per capita water available indicate that we are one of the most water stressed countries in the world but still need them the most as we are the largest irrigator. Another example is the high and ever-increasing air pollution that have negative impact on health, human capital etc. Hence the need to develop and implement a more resource efficient growth path focused on climate, GHG emissions etc.
- (b) Agriculture sector needs tremendous support to enable them to move from traditional ways of food and crop selection and cultivation to a modern way of managing crop cultivation that is resilient to climate change. Also, the food incentives/subsidies though introduced with good intention have become counter-productive due to inherent process complexity and does not provide the intended gains to farmers.
- (c) In a recent study it was evident that only 20 borrowers account for more than 16% of the total debt exposure leading to “debt concentration” risk. Such concentration will have a negative impact in the economy for others relying on banks, especially the small and medium sector. Further the write off for NPA was at \$28 billion last financial year which was approx. 33% above the previous year NPA write off. Therefore, there needs to be clear focus on how to avoid bad investments and at the same time fund social sectors. With this backdrop, the role of increased and involved participation by financial sector is crucial as it's efforts and good health is key to strengthening the other sectors and thereby the economy as a whole.
- (d) Interestingly, prosperity and poverty live side by side. India is simultaneously home to the 3rd largest number of billionaires in the world, together with the highest number of poor people in the world (extract from India: SCD, World Bank report 2018). Reducing the inequality is critical for achieving SDGs.

Most of these challenges could be solved if public and private investors do more focused investing by being socially responsible investors. It also requires a massive shift in mindset to focus from financial returns to more of a financial, social, environmental returns. With the global investors increasingly focusing on impact investing, we will also need to encourage our public and private investors on the same. It also means encouraging and building the capacity of our private sector corporates to be ready to receive the funding that fulfills the impact investing norms. The current focus is on how we can enable our investors to be more inclusive in making decisions on business or investments by combining financial returns with ESG aspects.

What are the key challenges for India in attaining SDGs? From an India perspective, we have the following key challenges:

- (a) Defining Indicators: History indicates that as a nation, we have not been very successful in setting relevant indicators to measure outcomes. Eg. food standards are poorly defined, quality education has been defined myopically, ‘safe water’ has no single definition. This leads to erroneous records and measurement e.g. hand pumps and tube wells are considered safe for drinking that led to believe that 86% Indians have access to safe drinking water which makes us “on track” for the SDG goal on drinking water.
- (b) Financing SDGs: Implementing SDGs in India by 2030 is estimated to cost around US\$15 trillion. Considering the government spends, India's GDP and all schemes related to SDGs, we have a funding gap of around US \$8-10 trillion. According to the United Nations MDG

- 2014 report, almost one-third of the world's 1.2 billion poor live in India, despite an economic growth of 6% plus. This emphasizes the importance of not just relying on domestic revenues but also the need to include private funding as a critical funding source for achieving SDGs.
- (c) **Monitoring and Ownership:** While NITI Aayog plays a significant role in tracking the progress of India's performance, each of the state government is also required to play a critical role. In addition, ownership is required not only from corporate and government but from people from all sides.
 - (d) **Measuring Progress/Data and definitions:** The challenge of measuring progress is critical and difficult. Non-availability of data (particularly in respect to informal sectors), periodicity issues and inadequate coverage of administrative data makes measurement of SDGs virtually impossible. Though we have made some progress, the assessment of ESG factors remains a challenge given the complexity of these aspects. There are also differences in ESG methodologies, and therefore the reporting and comparison becomes inconsistent. Lack of standardization creates hindrance in measuring non-financial performance.
 - (e) **Commitment from government and public:** Last but not the least, there needs to be a commitment from government and public and all stakeholders to make a shift in behavior towards focusing on achieving SDGs on anything we do- as that is the primary and key driver for achieving success.

Approach to a Sustainable India

With the above challenges as a backdrop and based on discussion with experts from the industry and scholars from academia, we propose to bridge the gap through the following four pillars:

1st Pillar: Regulation of Capital – recommended framework for change in government policy

2nd Pillar: Source of Capital - change in the way Financial institutions look at risk management with respect to ESG

3rd Pillar: Usage of capital - change in the way corporates look at conducting their business to make it sustainable

4th Pillar: Consumers - change the ethos of investment and create a reliable investing environment to promote investor confidence into green and clean products

Our recommendations should help catalyze the objective of most of these pillars and to an extent elevate India to reach her SDG 2030 target. We aim to do this through the following:

- (a) a unified classification or rating system for sustainable economic activities (supporting 1st pillar),
- (b) benchmarks and framework for financial institutions to appreciate and inculcate ESG related risk factors into their appraisal methodology (supporting 2nd pillar) and
- (c) a standard for corporates to reduce their carbon footprint (supporting 3rd pillar)
- (d) guidance to improve ESG related disclosure norms for financial institutions (supporting 4th pillar).

Recommendation#1: Unified rating system for sustainable economic activities

It is expected that in the coming years, ESG ratings will play a critical role in determining whether fund managers or exchange-traded funds buy the stock of a specific company or how much a company pays on its loans. It is critical to have a unified rating system for the ESG factors so that there is no ambiguity in terms of understanding the criteria and then tracking and monitoring it. For example, let's consider the Climate Change Performance Index (CCPI) (an index published by Germanwatch, the New Climate Institute and the Climate Action Network). The CCPI assesses each country's performance in four categories: GHG Emissions (40% of the overall score), Renewable

Energy (20%), Energy Use (20%) and Climate Policy (20%). They focus on 14 indicators relating to these four categories. In addition, the question is answered to what extent the respective country acts adequately in the areas of Emissions, Renewable Energies and Energy Use in order to achieve the Paris climate targets.

Such standardized indicators for the ESG activities, would help bringing in ease of implementing measures and monitoring them. For our mission to make India a major regional hub successful, banks and financial institutions need to play a critical role by providing capital and serving as a nexus in global financial networks.

To support more transparent ESG disclosures, we recommend that the National Stock Exchange should require all listed companies to report on sustainability, on a “comply or explain” basis. These type of “Responsible Financing Guidelines” built on good corporate governance, transparency and trust should help underpin India’s reputation as an investment heaven for social investors. A unified rating system will emphasize the need for responsible finance as banking sector continues to play a critical role in shaping sustainable economies.

Recommendation#2: Framework for financial institutions to include ESG related risk factors while appraising projects

Bank of America research found that ESG indicators monitoring could have helped avoid 90% of bankruptcies in the S&P 500 between 2005 and 2015, as it was observed that these companies had poor Environmental and Social scores for the 5 years before bankruptcy. An interview with CXOs of Indian corporates across TMT, Pharma, FMCG and Real Estate sectors reveal the importance of factors related to sustainability for long term prospect of the corporate. The same is echoed by Risk Managers and Credit underwriters of prominent financial institutions. While everybody understands the importance of accomplishing SDGs, there are several obstacles one must face when it comes to meeting these objectives.

During the years, many of the FIs have announced to no longer fund fossil energy projects or focus more on renewable energy projects/companies. We noted that there was recently a decision by one of the European central bank to divest from Australian government bonds because of the country’s high emissions dependency. It is a clear indication that central banks are increasingly focused on ESG factors and are being more responsible in investing.

Investor profiles are undergoing change with millennials and women, caring deeply about sustainability issues. Research estimates that ESG funds is expected to see growth of \$15 trillion to \$20 trillion, in the US market alone. In 2020, we expect ESG scores to be a determining factor for fund managers to buy a stock and for corporates to decide how much to pay for its loans.

We thus recommend a complete integration of ESG risk factors into credit assessment policy by incorporating principles of managing ESG in lending practices and capital market activities. The standard credit policy should be supplemented by a policy on “Responsible finance” that will provide structured guidance to tackle potential ESG risks. Specific sector guides need to be established to provide guidance on pertinent risks related to the industry. For all other cases, impact of ESG on valuation of the asset or collateral should be taken into consideration and pricing of the asset need to be linked to adherence of SDG standards on a regular basis.

Framework of ESG Risk Management for a Lender

Objective

- Support clients who demonstrate commitment to build capacity to manage ESG risks in their business
- Work with clients to help build their capacity and knowledge on the international best practices and encourage initiatives within

- Portfolio level approach to minimize credit in certain sectors and encourage credit in others that will thrive in the long run from a sustainable perspective.

Governance Structure

Board should take overall responsibility of driving sustainability initiatives in the organization and run this through a Sustainability council, headed by the CEO and having representation from all departments.

Scope and Commitment to uphold the above-mentioned objectives:

- This should ideally apply to all lending and capital market products across subsidiaries and geographies.
- Consider ESG parameters into financing decisions to avoid or mitigate negative impacts
- Portfolio based approach to identify high impact sectors and apply enhanced due diligence
 - o Prohibited transactions like i) Burning forests to clear land, ii) Usage of child labour and human rights abuse in the supply chain, iii) involving in production of military goods and artillery used in warfare including but not restricted to weapons of mass destruction, iv) trading in wildlife and other exotic species
 - o Call for immediate action if clients in the portfolio are found to be directly or indirectly associated with the above activities

ESG Risk Management Overview

ESG Related Sensitive Industries (Sector-Specific Approach to Achieve Maximum Impact While Trying to Attain Responsible Financing Standards)

Watch-listed Credits (guidance to mitigate risk while financing clients in high-impact sectors) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chemicals • Energy from fossil fuels like Non-renewable sources of Power , Oil& Gas • Mining and Metals • Agriculture like certain Agri-commodities, Palm oil, etc. 	Negative Credits <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Products related to Defence or Military equipment • Forestry
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specific Sector guides • ESG Risk management template 	Generic ESG Risk management template

Banks or NBFs may like to follow the below guidelines while appraising a new or existing project. This is to be used in conjunction with existing credit policy and extant regulations to appropriately assess ESG risks and accordingly value the asset or underlying collateral.

Sustainable Finance Framework for Banks and Financial Institutions

ESG Themes	Indicators of Best practice to manage Risk	Rationale for using the indicator
Sector focus		
Is the funding part of Negative sector	Bank's credit policy of negative sectors	Compliance of Policy guidelines
High Emitting sector exposure (supply chain)	Quantum of revenue associated	Impact on SDG

Percentage exposure to green economy	Quantum of revenue associated	Impact on SDG
Policy changes/tax reforms	Tax advantage for Banks and FI focussing on social sectors	
Portfolio		
Responsible finance	Percentage of portfolio in Green Finance	
SDG related Risk management	Consider environmental factors in appraising Risk	Quantify SDG risk to business
Loan pricing based on fulfillment of ESG goals	Return on SDG related Risk capital	True risk based returns
New fund raising tools for focus on underserved segments	Social bonds, luring impact investing investors	
Client's Approach to ESG issues		
Diversity and Inclusion		
Gender equality across the organisation including Board representation	Percentage of total employees including those at the top	To bring about harmony with society
Percentage of differently abled and non-straight employees	Percentage of total employees	To bring about harmony with society
Community service		
Specific paid leave for community service	Privilege for community service	Encourage importance of such service
Specific CSR fund allocation	Specific funding from institutions on social projects	
Staff training and encouragement to undertake SGD initiatives	SDG certifications and Responsible finance council	Developing relevant skillsets
Environment		
Reduction in GHG emissions	Carbon footprint	Become carbon negative
Water management and efficiency	Proportion of recycled water	
Energy consumption	Proportion of energy from non-renewable source	

Recommendation#3: A Fresh Perspective of Looking at a Going Concern, Monitoring Carbon Footprint

Definition and Measurement

Greenhouse Gas emissions is the most important challenge today to tackle climate change and contain the rise in temperature to below 2°C, as per the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change. Thus, emissions resulting out of a company's operations are the key indicators of assessing a company's exposure to climate risks. The ideal approach to be followed is a life-cycle approach where we calculate the following

- Impact of its internal production processes
- Climate risk to the supply chain it uses,
- Quantity and nature of the energy it consumes (inputs)
- Category of products and services it sells (outputs)
- Resultant exposure of those to climate related risks when customers use them.

This measure of GHG emissions is called ‘carbon footprint’. As per the GHG Protocol, there are three types of GHG emissions:

- (a) Scope 1 emissions: All direct emissions caused by the company
- (b) Scope 2 emissions: Indirect emissions from consumption of electricity, heat or steam, etc.
- (c) Scope 3 emissions: Other indirect emissions, such as usage of supply chain, transport- related activities, electricity-related activities, outsourced activities, use of sold products, waste disposal, etc.

International and European standards like ISO 14064 on standards for greenhouse gas accounting and verification, and the Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) and Organization Environmental Footprint (OEF), are available measures to calculate scope 3 emissions.

Measuring Carbon Footprint

- (a) First, we should ensure consistency, comparability and quality of data pertaining to GHG emissions.
- (b) Second, regulators should ensure that data on all three scopes of emissions is obtained prudentially and complies with the GHG Protocol or ISO 14064 and ISO 14069.
- (c) Third, regulators should encourage initiatives taken by sectors against Scope 3 emissions, especially those with high stakes on climate change and its mitigation (e.g. oil & gas, mining, transportation, etc).
- (d) The entity should disclose the methodology used to base its estimates (i.e. bottom-up or top-down approach, state underlying assumptions and precautionary principles mention the research methodology used to estimate missing, unreported, and underreported emissions).

The regulator should disclose the financial metric that need to be used for normalizing GHG emissions in a given currency. Generally, benchmark B composed with N assets has a carbon intensity of:

Carbon Intensity ToT (CI) = $i = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \text{Carbon Intensity ToT (i)} * w_i * K_s$ where

- Carbon Intensity ToT (i) = GHG tot / Financial Metric (i) is the total carbon intensity of asset ‘i’ in tonnes of CO₂ per year per Million INR for which all the related scopes are accounted for
- w_i is the weight of the asset in the portfolio or index
- K_s is a constant depending on the sector. The factor K_s , called the Sree factor, is arrived at by regressing the extent of carbon the top 20 industries in a sector emits / the total emission coming from all sectors.

For Financial Metric, There are Primarily three Different Kinds of Approaches

- (a) Flow financial metrics: for corporates, use revenues and for sovereigns, use GDP
- (b) Stock financial metrics: for corporates, use market cap and enterprise value and for sovereigns, use quantum of issued debt
- (c) Accounting metrics: across asset classes, we can use total capital which is a combination of debt and equity

Key Points to Consider

- (a) Using revenue helps corporates decarbonize their business by adopting practices to generate low CHG emissions / unit of revenue.
- (b) In order to avoid window dressing, Index’ carbon intensity should be calculated using average weights on a quarterly basis.
- (c) Management of double counting – we should be careful to ensure that we don’t double count.

This can be achieved by taking the share of value addition done by a player in the value chain of the product and then split the emissions accordingly.

Another essential aspect of carbon math is the difference between being “carbon neutral” and being “net zero” or better being “carbon negative”. While they may sound similar, they in fact are quite different.

- (a) Corporates have typically claimed to be “carbon neutral” if they could offset their emissions with payments that result in reduction of emissions or removal of carbon from the atmosphere. Eg. one way to encourage reduction in emissions is to pay someone for not deforesting the land they own. This is a noble approach, but in effect it pays someone to prevent a negative environmental impact. It doesn’t lead to afforestation that may have remove carbon and have a positive impact.
- (b) In contrast, “net zero” refers to removal of as much carbon as it emits. The phrase is “net zero” and not just “zero” because while carbon emissions continue, these are equal to carbon removal.
- (c) “Carbon negative” is the best approach and refers to a situation where a company takes measures to remove more carbon than it can possibly emit each year. This is an area where companies who are front-runners in the industry should take initiatives to go from being carbon neutral to net-zero and finally carbon-negative. In fact, many corporates have taken the lead and quite a few of them have pledged to be become carbon-negative by 2030 across sectors.

Recommendation#4: Guidance to improve ESG related disclosure norms for financial institutions.

ESG-oriented investing has experienced a meteoric rise, with global sustainable investment now topping \$30 trillion. We see that even Private Equity firms are willing and getting ready to be part of the ESG drive. For example, we read that some of the world’s largest firms, KKR, Partners Group, TPG, have signed up to be adopters of the “Operating Principles for Impact Management” published by IFC. This will enable these firms to report on the positive environmental, social and governance impacts of their investments, as well as their potentially negative effects. They have developed multiple funds and investment strategies focused on the SDGs.

In order to take this forward, we need to promote an environment of trust and consistency in which sound investment decisions can be made with reliance and confidence. Consistent reporting and benchmarking will extend comparability across financial markets and products, thereby enabling prudent decision making. Thus, we propose the need for financial institutions to come up with pre- defined disclosures for the individual assets as well as for the portfolio. Since different entities have different impact on sustainability factors, it is imperative for the entities to aggregate the various ESG factors for the purpose of disclosure. We have listed below a set of ESG factors for different classes of financial institutions:

	Disclosure Factors (reporting requirement is weighted average at the index)	Key Asset Classes			Other Asset Classes		
		Equities	Fixed Income : Asset backed securities	Fixed Income : Bonds	Hedge funds	Commodities	Private Funding
Overall disclosure	Consolidated ESG rating	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
	UNGC violations %	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes
	International standard signatories %	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No
Environmental Disclosure	Consolidated environmental rating	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No
	Carbon intensity	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes
	%age exposure (direct / indirect) to Fossil fuels	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	Yes
	%age of Green revenue	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
	%age of Green Bonds in the entire structure	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Social Disclosure	%age exposure to climate related health risks	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Consolidated social rating	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
	% age of Social violation evident in the last 1 year	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
	% age investment in sectors directly or indirectly related to weapons	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
	%age investment related to tobacco	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Weighted portfolio rank as per OHCHR Human Rights Indicator	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Gini coefficient to measure Income inequality	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Governance Disclosure	Freedom of expression - sampling across the portfolio	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
	Consolidated Governance rating	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No
	% age of independent Board members	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No
	% age of diversity seen at the Board and top management level	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No
	Corruption perception index as measured by Transparency International	No	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No
	Political stability in the country of operation	No	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No
	Rule of law	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	No
Ease of doing business as defined by WB scale	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	

Necessary Requirements

- For all disclosures, the percentage of portfolio coverage has to be reported
- Information as mentioned above need to be at the benchmark level, published as an aggregated, weighted average value

Conclusion

To be sustainable, companies need to focus on “PPP”- planet, people and profit and not just profit. Gone are the days when we humans could afford to spend a day or a nickel on sustainable initiatives. The world of today needs a more concerted effort to internalize ESG in everything we do, both financial and non-financial. Today, ESG plays a pivotal role in driving consumer preference and they are ready to pay premium to “go green”. Almost a third of Unilever consumers are now making their buying decisions based on the brands’ environmental and social impact.

According to McKinsey, 70% of consumers across multiple industries like automotive, building, electronics, and packaging have agreed to pay an additional 5% for a green product if the product’s performance standards are same as a non-green alternative.

The same has percolated to the financial sector that arguably plays the most prominent role in channelizing clean and green capital in the right areas. Consequently, we see several FIs, DFIs coming up with social bonds like green bonds, climate bonds, blue bonds (for marine life) etc where the proceeds are invested in business that are high on ESG standards. Several corporates are committed to become carbon negative by 2030.

But with issues around standardization, benchmarking, sustainable profit ventures, we have miles to go before we sleep. Our governments and private sector need to work hand in hand while planning to convert us into a sustainable economy by 2030. We believe that implementation of some or all of our recommendations would definitely help us reach our goal within a desirable timeframe. We thus strive to create awareness of these targets and its benefits to all stakeholders in the nation.

We feel that large investors are at an advantage to move the needle in the right track by directing businesses and corporates to follow and adhere to sustainable practices. But all the stakeholders – investors, governments, corporates, consumers and general public – must act responsibly considering the effects of their actions.

The journey to achieving SDGs is long, but with the right motivation, efforts and participation by all, it is achievable. As indicated at World Economic Forum (WEF): no human technology can replace “nature’s technology”, perfected over hundreds of millions of years to sustain life on Earth.

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Appendix-1

Overview of respondents

Location	Economist	Corporate	FI/Banks	Asset Manager	Total
USA	3	1		1	5
India		3	4		7
Singapore			2		2
Europe			1		1
Total	3	4	7	1	15

Some of the Key Interview Questions

- What are some of the key sectors to focus for achieving SDGs in India?
- Is funding gap the key challenge for achieving SDG in India? If yes, then what strategies are followed by other developing countries to plug the funding gap for SDGs?
- What should bank and other FIs do to ensure they route their capital towards SDG initiatives?
- What framework is available to Monitor SDG performance of corporates? What work has happened to standardize some of the key indicators?
- We have the GAAP for accounting. Could we not develop (or is it already available) something like GAAP for SDGs?
- How do we quantify metrics used to capture progress towards SDG for a corporate or country?
- Do you agree to the recommendations suggested for achieving of SDGs in India?

- What are the key steps to be taken in implementing some of the recommendations?
- What would be your suggestion on ways we can influence stakeholders to be more socially responsible?

Appendix -2

Snapshot of the survey done with corporates, educationists and policy makers on the best way to make achievement of SDGs successful for India

Appendix -3

We ran our recommendations past policy makers, economists and corporates to understand their views on how easy or difficult it is easy to implement these. The response as shown below is from the perspective of implementing the same in India, taking into consideration demographic challenges, economic position, fiscal and current account deficit. We however, repose faith in our recommendations and piloted the same while executing deals in certain financial institutions. While we await long term results, we have seen significant progress and positive impact in the short term.

Appendix-4

Why we focused on financial sector

Background: The Indian banking system consists of 27 public sector banks, 21 private sector banks, 49 foreign banks, 56 regional rural banks, 1,562 urban cooperative banks and 94,384 rural cooperative banks, in addition to cooperative credit institutions (FY17 data). In FY07-18, total lending increased at a CAGR of 10.94 per cent and total deposits increased at a CAGR of 11.66 per cent. India’s retail credit market is the fourth largest in the emerging countries. It increased to US\$ 281 billion on December 2017 from US\$ 181 billion on December 2014. The financial sector is key to the general health of the economy as its performance is critical for all sectors. (extract from RBI website)

Source: RBI website